

Benefits of Entrepreneurship, an Analysis for Its Determination

Dr. J. Emilio Méndez-González, M. A. R. H. Liliana Álvarez-Loya,
M. A. R. H. Enrique Guzmán-Nieves, Dr. Xóchitl Bustillos-Varela

Fulltime Teacher in Strategic Management, Administrative Audit,
Entrepreneurship and Management in Autonomous University of Chihuahua, México

ABSTRACT

This study seeks to analyze the benefits of undertaking from the University, which is divided into three stages, students from first to third semester, from fourth to seventh and from sixth to ninth, seeking to compare the way they see entrepreneurship at the beginning of their instruction, in the development of their academic preparation and in the last stage of business training.

The small enterprises represent for Mexico 51% of its Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and the development of 72% of the generation of jobs through micro, small and medium entrepreneurs, for this reason the institutions of higher level must adapt new strategies of business training and thus contribute in a relevant way to the economic development of the country.

KEYWORDS: *Formal Entrepreneurship, Self-employment, Business in Progress, Business Opportunity*

How to cite this paper: Dr. J. Emilio Méndez-González | M. A. R. H. Liliana Álvarez-Loya | M. A. R. H. Enrique Guzmán-Nieves | Dr. Xóchitl Bustillos-Varela "Benefits of Entrepreneurship, an Analysis for Its Determination" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-6 | Issue-1, December 2021, pp.1684-1688, URL: www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd49095.pdf

Copyright © 2021 by author (s) and International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development Journal. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0) (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>)

I. INTRODUCTION

In many countries the participation of micro, small and medium-sized enterprises represent a large percentage of their Gross Domestic Product (GDP), the economic spill over and the engine of it is born in the decision to form a company, to generate direct and indirect sources of employment that ultimately become the economy of a country. The GEM (2021) [1] defines entrepreneurship as: "any attempt to create new businesses or new enterprises, such as self-employment, a new business organization or the expansion of an existing business, by an individual, a team of individuals or an established business".

The economy is based on a percentage of 36.38% of adults aged 18 to 64 who perceive opportunities, 50.07% who believe they have the knowledge and skills to undertake, 28.40% with fear of failure and 50.67% who see entrepreneurship as a good career choice.

In advanced semesters, students must all take a subject called Development of Entrepreneurs, which seeks to generate entrepreneurship in students by developing skills necessary for the start of a company. However, it is up to each university student to make the decision to form a company.

Being an entrepreneur, not only offers benefits to those who undertake, but also supports the same community in which they are inserted, with the creation of jobs, promotion of the economy and helping to "minimize the adverse and structural factors that force people to leave their country of origin" UNESCO [3], within this same document in goal 4.4 it is established by 2030 to increase the number of young people and adults Trained... to access employment, decent work and entrepreneurship, further highlighting the importance it has.

The economy is based on resources or based on innovation, in the case of Mexico according to the GEM [1], for point 1 there is a percentage of 36.38% of adults from 18 to 64 years old who perceive opportunities, 50.07% who believe they have the knowledge and skills to undertake, 28.40% with fear of failure and 50.67% who see entrepreneurship as a good career choice.

II. THEORETICAL AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

In Mexico, according to Guerrero, Urbano, Ramos, Ruiz-Navarro, Neira, & Fernández-Laviada et al. (2016) [4], 21% of students have already created a company, 42% have entrepreneurial parents and of these, 27% are or have been entrepreneurs, mentions that 25% of men have been entrepreneurs against 17% of women, the IDB (2018) [5] says that the profile of creative entrepreneurs in Latin America: they are mostly men (61.8%) and in their minority women (38.2%). The average age of the creative entrepreneur is 35 years, and 90.4% have university studies, these differences are clear from understanding that the first study is specific to Mexico, while the second includes all of Latin America.

As stated by Guerrero et al. (2016) [4] university students in Mexico have a very positive attitude towards entrepreneurship, they perceive it as an enriching professional option that will give satisfaction in their working life, 49.7% of these, have started a company, 54.4% believe they have the knowledge and skills necessary to undertake, and 29.8% feel fear of failure in their projects, 65% say they want to undertake in the short term and 50% say they have received some type of training in this regard, data that are consistent with the aforementioned information of the GEM (2021) [1] and presents small differences.

This last data, of those who have received training in this regard, contrasts with what the IDB (2018) [5] says, according to the data of this study, entrepreneurs in general learned to do business “on the fly”, that is, during the very process of gestation of their company, that is, that despite having received some training or training in their professional training, this was not adequate or was insufficient.

Different authors Guerrero et al. (2016), González et al. (2017), mention as important factors: age, schooling, sex, profession of parents, among others to make the decision to become an entrepreneur or decide not to try.

Leyva-Carreras et al. (2021) [8] in their study proposed to measure the relationship between

personal, intellectual and social skills with the skills of achievement for the entrepreneur perceived by students at the undergraduate level, for which they established the following criteria: Within personal skills self-confidence, within intellectual skills the ability to identify problems and within social skills teamwork.

- Intellectuals.
- Ability to identify problems.
- Social.
- Teamwork.

Two variables are mentioned, the entrepreneurial profile, which is formed from the attitudes, aptitudes and skills of the individual, as well as an entrepreneurial spirit, which will be developed within his stay as a university student. These skills have to be complemented with another group of abilities such as: individual values, creativity, initiative, self-confidence, energy and ability to work, perseverance, leadership, risk acceptance, the need for achievement, tolerance for change and problem management.

In this research, through surveys to measure personal, intellectual and social skills, the authors were able to conclude that achievement in entrepreneurship is based on confidence skills, ability to identify problems and teamwork, however, they also note the need for the University of Sonora, Mexico to implement a profile model for the development of entrepreneurial skills.

For its part, the Inter-American Institute for Cooperation on Agriculture (IICA, 2009) [14] identifies ten characteristics of entrepreneurial behavior, grouped into three areas:

- Achievement-oriented features:
 1. Search for opportunities and constant initiative
 2. Persistencia
 3. Cumplimiento
 4. Search for efficiency and quality
 5. Taking calculated risks
- Planner features:
 6. Set goals
 7. Search for information
 8. Systematic planning and monitoring
- Power characteristics:
 9. Persuasion and support networks
 10. Self-confidence and independence

These skills are directly related to those mentioned above and there are direct coincidences such as self-confidence, risk and planning.

For Serida et al. (2017) [11], this would show that entrepreneurial perceptions and attitudes would respond more to cultural and political aspects of a

region rather than to economic models and the level of development of countries.

The OECD (2021) [2], in the biennial publication examines how public policies at national, regional and local levels can support job creation by encouraging business start-ups and self-employment by people from disadvantaged or under-represented social groups (e.g. women, youth, seniors, the unemployed, immigrants, people with disabilities). The reports present self-employment and entrepreneurship indicators for these groups, including self-employment rates, growth expectations, entrepreneurship skills and more. The reports also contain thematic policy chapters and country profiles that highlight hot issues and recent policy developments.

Being an entrepreneur, not only offers benefits to those who undertake, but also supports the same community in which they are inserted, with the creation of jobs, promotion of the economy and helping to “minimize the adverse and structural factors that force people to leave their country of origin” (UNESCO 2019) [3], within this same document in goal 4.4 it is established by 2030 to increase the number of young people and adults Trained... to access employment, decent work and entrepreneurship, further highlighting the importance it has.

For Fernández-Laviada et al. (2014) [7] the variables of gender, age and occupation of parents do not influence the student's decision to create a company, contrasting with the statements made above.

III. DISCUSSION AND PROPOSALS FOR SOLUTION

Some of the most important factors to decide to undertake are: The greatest motivation to be an entrepreneur is the satisfaction that would mean having their own company, the image and importance of being an entrepreneur in society, the influence exerted by the media, personal independence and personal or family security.

Among the factors that limit entrepreneurship, there are natural elements such as total ignorance of the steps to follow, in addition to the fear of failure is presented as one of the main limitations to be able to undertake, economic risks, limited time for other activities and tax burdens.

The perception of students about entrepreneurship is intimately related to their own knowledge and personal, sociocultural and cognitive skills, even with their maturity, as stated by Salvatorio (2012) [9] at an older age, it is more punctual and objective in the

appraisals related to the evaluation of the fulfillment of objectives in a company.

In the entrepreneurial profile, two variables are mentioned, which is formed from the attitudes, aptitudes and skills of the individual, as well as an entrepreneurial spirit, which will be developed within his stay as a university student. These skills have to be complemented with another group of abilities such as: individual values, creativity, initiative, self-confidence, energy and ability to work, perseverance, leadership, risk acceptance, the need for achievement, tolerance for change and problem management. (Kantis (2010), Pablo-Martí and García-Tabuena, (2006)), cited by Leyva-Carreras et al. (2021) [8].

Different authors Guerrero et al. [4] and González et al. [6], mention as important factors: age, schooling, sex, profession of parents, among others to make the decision to become an entrepreneur or decide not to try.

For Fernández-Laviada et al. [7] the variables of gender, age and occupation of the parents do not influence the student's decision to create a company, contrasting with the statements made above.

Leyva et al. (2019) [8] in their study set out to measure the relationship between personal, intellectual and social skills and achievement skills for the entrepreneur perceived by undergraduate students, for which they established the following criteria: Within personal skills self-confidence, within intellectual skills the ability to identify problems and within the Social teamwork.

According to Guerrero et al. [4] the areas where more entrepreneurship is carried out are the social sciences has the advantage with 24%, they mention that Mexican students have a more positive attitude towards entrepreneurship, they also see in their universities a positive environment that develops their abilities to identify business opportunities", under this assumption, universities have a strong commitment to continue to be generators of new and better programs that promote this spirit of economic growth

The focus of the Autonomous University of Chihuahua is on the situation of entrepreneurship in Mexico.

The commitment of the university is to create the most favorable conditions for entrepreneurship to develop, hoping that this work begins to chart the path to identify the perception of its students about entrepreneurship and the skills, attitudes and knowledge necessary for its development.

The perception that each individual has about entrepreneurship can be determined in three

indicators, namely, according to Serida et al. (2017) [11]

1. The consideration that in the next six months there will be conditions to start a business
2. The perception of having the knowledge and skills necessary to undertake
3. The fear of failure.

On the other hand, the perception that society as a whole has been also valued:

1. Perception of entrepreneurship as a good career choice
2. The status and prestige of starting a business
3. The media attention given to entrepreneurship.

In conclusion, it is possible to determine that the most important relationship between the variables analyzed are those related to the fact that more than 60% of students at all levels are willing to start a business; also more than 60% of respondents have a history of entrepreneurship in their family, so it is possible to infer that the choice of a career related to business, is influenced by your family support or referral; another important relationship is the condition that they consider that entrepreneurs should have, and it is without a doubt, the passion for the project in progress; the type of business that students consider most likely to be able to undertake, is one with innovative, rather than traditional, characteristics, which denotes a great influence of progress and new trends; the main reason why students would start a business is to have economic freedom, followed by becoming their own bosses; Another point of analysis, is given in the perception of opportunities and external supports that they perceive and is given with relevant result in the financial needs and training or professional preparation, finally, the lack of resources, they consider that it is the most important barrier, more than in the attitude and the lack of professional or academic preparation.

REFERENCES:

- [1] GEM. (2021). Global Entrepreneurship Monitor 2020/2021. Available November 13, 2021, at: <https://www.gemconsortium.org/report/gem-20202021-global-report>
- [2] OECD. (2021). The Missing Entrepreneurs [Internet] Available November 13, 2021, at: https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/employment/the-missing-entrepreneurs-2021_71b7a9bb-en, <https://www.oecdilibrary.org/docserver/71b7a9bb-en.pdf>
ISSN: 26644851 (online)
<https://doi.org/10.1787/43c2f41c-en>
- [3] UNESCO. (2021). Global Education Monitoring Report 2021: Migration, Displacement and Education. Building Bridges, not Walls. Paris: UNESCO. [Internet] Available November 13, 2021, from <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000367436/PDF/367436en.pdf.multi>
- [4] Guerrero, M., Urbano, D., Ramos, A. R., Ruiz-Navarro, J., Neira, I., & Fernández-Laviada, A. (2016). Entrepreneurial profile of the university student. University Entrepreneurship Observatory in Spain. Madrid: Crue Spanish Universities-Red Emprendia-CISE. [Internet] Available November 13, 2021, at: https://www.crue.org/Documentos%20compartidos/Publicaciones/Observatorio%20de%20Emprendimiento%20Universitario/20161201_Observatorio%20de%20Emprendimiento%20Universitario_informe_web.pdf
- [5] IDB. (2018). Undertake an orange future. [Internet] Available November 13, 2021, at: The Inter-American Development Bank: <https://publications.iadb.org/publications/spanish/document/Emprender-un-futuro-naranja-Quince-preguntas-para-entender-mejor-a-creative-entrepreneurs-in-Am%C3%A9rica-Latina-y-el-Caribe.pdf>
- [6] González Sánchez, R., Torres Preciado, V., & Tinoco Zermeño, M. Á. (2017). Empirical analysis of the determinants of entrepreneurship in university students: The case of the University of Colima in Mexico. *Economy and Society*, XXI (36), 43-59. [Internet] Available November 13, 2021, at: <https://www.redalyc.org/articulo.oa?id=510/51052064003>
- [7] Fernández-Laviada, A., Rueda Sampedro, M. I., & Herrero Crespo, Á. (2014). Study of the entrepreneurial attitude of university students of the faculty of CC.EE. and business of Cantabria. *Memories of the Ibero-American Congress of Science, Technology, Innovation and Education*. Buenos Aires, Argentina. [Internet] Available November 13, 2021, at: http://www.aeca1.org/pub/on_line/comunicaciones_xvicongresoaecca/cd/36f.pdf
- [8] Leyva-Carreras, A. B., Alcántara-Castelo, J. R., Espejel-Blanco, J. E., & Coronado-García, M. A. (2021). Training of the entrepreneurial profile in higher education at the University of Sonora. *School of Business Administration Magazine* (86). [Internet] Available at:

- <https://doi.org/10.21158/01208160.n86.2021.2293>
- [9] Salvatorio, A. M. (2012). Personality and intelligence characteristics associated with entrepreneurs in an institution of higher education. Doctoral thesis. Mexico: National Autonomous University of Mexico. [Internet] Available November 13, 2021, at: <https://132.248.9.195/ptd2012/mayo/0680699/1ndex.html>
- [10] Autonomous University of Chihuahua. (2018). UACH Retrieved on November 12, 2021, from Basic Statistics: Administration 2016-2022: [Internet] Available at: https://uach.mx/assets/media/publicaciones/2017/10/143_agenda-estadistica/estadistica-basica-2018-2021.pdf
- [11] Serida, J., Guerrero, C., Alzamora, J., Borda, A., & Morales, O. (2017). Global entrepreneurship monitor: Peru 2106-217. Retrieved on November 13, 2021, from ESAN Graduate School of Business: <https://www.esan.edu.pe/publicaciones/2017/10/12/GEM%202016-2017%20VF.pdf>
- [12] López Loyola, J. E. (July 10, 2014). Say no to "entrepreneurship." Forbes Mexico [Internet] Available November 13, 2021, at: <http://www.forbes.com.mx/di-al-emprededurismo>
- [13] Spanish Royal Academy. (2021). Spanish language dictionary, version 23.3 online. [Internet] Available November 13, 2021, at: <https://dle.rae.es/emprender#6Snvqcg>
- [14] IICA. (2009). Young entrepreneurs: Committed to the Sustainable Development of Rural Territories. (M. O. Beltrán., Ed.) Quito, Ecuador: Inter-American Institute for Cooperation on Agriculture.

